

1 **Title:**

2 “Close-to-Nature management of tropical timber plantations is economically viable and provides
3 biodiversity benefits”

4
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14 **Abstract**

15 Reforestation of tropical forests is crucial to mitigate the climate crisis and restore ecosystems.
16 However, past efforts have been criticized for establishing monoculture timber plantations with exotic
17 tree species. Close-to-Nature (CTN) practices aim to minimize negative forest management impacts on
18 forests ecosystems by mimicking natural dynamics. So far, CTN management practices are rarely
19 applied in tropical plantation forestry. This study evaluates the economic, carbon sequestration, and
20 biodiversity potential of CTN management in tropical mixed-species plantations in Central America
21 using a simulation-optimization approach. CTN practices such as *selective harvesting*, *retention*
22 *forestry*, and *shelterwood cutting* of mixed species stands were compared to even-aged mixtures and
23 conventional monoculture practices. Results showed that CTN management was economically viable
24 for certain species mixtures and management practices at an 8 % discount rate and had the potential
25 to increase carbon storage and biodiversity in the modeled plantations. At current carbon prices, CTN-

26 managed plantations may only become financially competitive with monocultures, if monocultures are
27 excluded from carbon certification schemes that increasingly aim at co-producing non-carbon benefits
28 like biodiversity conservation. If carbon prices increase, the sale of carbon credits could finance the
29 transformation of monocultures to CTN-managed mixed-species stands. The competitiveness of CTN
30 management could also be improved through performance-based biodiversity payments, such as the
31 sale of biodiversity credits.

32

Preprint

33 1. Introduction

34 Recent climate change and biodiversity reports have concluded that following current trajectories the
35 world will not be able to meet its climate or biodiversity sustainability goals (IPBES, 2019; IPCC, 2018).
36 Large-scale reforestation and restoration of tropical forest landscapes has emerged as one important
37 strategy to mitigate the global climate crisis through the sequestration of carbon while also restoring
38 important habitats and other ecosystem functions (Bastin et al., 2019; Griscom et al., 2017; IPBES,
39 2019). Past reforestation efforts have been criticized for the widespread establishment of exotic-
40 species monoculture timber plantations with a limited long-term carbon sequestration potential and
41 limited biodiversity value (Lewis et al., 2019). Nonetheless, the area of tropical timber plantations is
42 expected to increase further (FAO, 2020). Studies have repeatedly highlighted that the carbon
43 sequestration potential of tropical timber plantations could be increased substantially through
44 management adaptations, such as extended rotation times and maintaining higher stand densities
45 (Nölte et al., 2018; Olschewski and Benítez, 2010; Pinnschmidt et al., 2023; Quintero-Méndez and
46 Jerez-Rico, 2017). From a biodiversity perspective, plantation forests can offer more suitable habitats
47 for native forest species than competing agricultural land uses (Barlow et al., 2007; Brockerhoff et al.,
48 2008; Stephens and Wagner, 2007). A wide variety of measures can be taken to enhance biodiversity
49 in plantation forests, such as using multiple (native) tree species, establishing mixed-species stands,
50 preventing large-scale clearcutting, and leaving patches of trees or individual mature trees
51 unharvested (Brockerhoff et al., 2008; Carnus et al., 2006; Di Sacco et al., 2021; Gustafsson et al., 2012).
52 The consideration of multiple forest management objectives has led to the development of many
53 different “Close-to-Nature” (CTN) forest management strategies, especially for managed temperate
54 forests (Pommerening and Murphy, 2004; Pukkala and von Gadow, 2012). CTN management practices
55 seek to mimic the ecological dynamics of natural forests and minimize negative impacts of forest
56 management activities, while fulfilling key management objectives, such as timber production.
57 Accordingly, CTN forest management spans a wide range of management strategies but for this study
58 we consider CTN forest management practices to be characterized by the absence of large-scale

59 clearcutting events, the use of multiple tree species, and/or the maintenance of an uneven-aged stand
60 structure.

61 So far, the application of CTN management practices to the context of tropical timber plantations has
62 not been studied extensively (Maennicke and Griess, 2019). Importantly, studies on the financial
63 implications of CTN practices in tropical plantation forests are currently absent. Such studies are a
64 crucial first step in the development of tropical CTN plantations, as financial considerations – i.e.
65 expected profitability of plantations – remain the most important drivers of investments into tropical
66 plantation forests (Da Silva et al., 2017). Recent studies have suggested that monoculture and mixed-
67 species plantations of native tree species might be an economically competitive alternative to exotic
68 species monoculture plantations in Central America (Griess and Knoke, 2011; Pinnschmidt et al., 2022;
69 Piotto et al., 2010; Sinacore et al., 2022; Streed et al., 2006). Pinnschmidt et al. (2023) further
70 suggested that mixed stands might outperform monocultures substantially if also payments for carbon
71 credits were considered in the valuation. While these results are promising, the studies only
72 considered native species monoculture and mixed-species plantations managed as even-aged stands
73 with reoccurring clear-cutting activities. The economic potential of uneven-aged management
74 practices without clearcutting has been studied more extensively for temperate and boreal forests
75 (Hanewinkel, 2002; Knoke, 2012). Here, studies have shown that uneven-aged management practices
76 *can* be economically advantageous under a wide variety of conditions, and due to many different
77 factors. For example, applying selective harvesting practices (i.e. periodically harvesting individual
78 trees instead of clearcutting) can ensure that individual trees are harvested closer to their economic
79 optimum; more frequent harvesting events and the resulting temporal diversification of revenues
80 might reduce risk from timber market fluctuations; the presence of fewer trees in the dominant canopy
81 layer might increase growth rates for the largest (and accordingly most valuable) trees in an uneven-
82 aged stand (Hanewinkel et al., 2014; Pukkala, 2015; Roessiger et al., 2011).

83

84 In this study, we aim to determine the economic potential of CTN management practices in the context
85 of commercial tropical plantation forestry. We further aim to estimate the potential of such
86 management practices to increase the carbon sequestration and biodiversity potential of tropical
87 plantation forests. We will do so by applying a simulation-optimization approach extending on a forest
88 economic model previously published by Pinnschmidt et al. (2023, 2022). Specifically, we will simulate
89 and optimize the application of CTN management practices including selective harvesting, retention
90 forestry, and shelterwood cutting in tropical mixed-species plantations in Central America. We will
91 then compare the economic, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity performance of these stands
92 against conventionally managed even-aged monocultures.

93

94 2. Methodology

95 The study consists of two parts: First, we optimized the management of CTN-managed stands with
96 regard to maximizing the stands' economic performance, considering both revenues generated
97 through timber sales and the sale of carbon credits. We then compared the economic, carbon
98 sequestration, and biodiversity performance of the optimized CTN-managed stands against
99 conventionally managed monoculture stands.

100 To apply the simulation-optimization approach, we had to extend the forest economic model of
101 Pinnschmidt et al. (2023, 2022) by integrating CTN management options. The model is suitable to
102 simulate both monoculture and mixed-species stands by combining a process-based forest growth
103 model (*3PGmix*) with detailed economic and operational data. So far, the model only allowed for even-
104 aged management options (i.e. clear-cut harvesting). For the later comparison between monoculture
105 and CTN-managed stands, we further extended the model by adding a biodiversity module to estimate
106 selected biodiversity indicators based on the model's growth outputs. Figure 1 gives an overview of
107 the extended model.

108

109 Figure 1 Overview of modeling components, data, and data flows of the forest economic model used in this study. Bullet points
 110 give examples of important modeling steps and data in the different model components.

111

112 2.1 Case study: Close-to-Nature management of mixed-species plantations in Costa Rica

113 We conducted our analysis based on a plantation site in northern Costa Rica (10.96551, -85.05070).

114 The site is characterized by tropical moist forest conditions with an average yearly precipitation of

115 2221 mm/m² and average temperatures ranging between 21-35 °C. The site was previously used as a

116 cattle pasture but was reforested with both monoculture and mixed-species timber plantations. In the

117 mixtures, 2 or 3 tree species were mixed tree by tree. For our study, we selected 4 mixed-species

118 stands of the species *Tectona grandis*, *Vochysia guatemalensis*, *Hieronyma alchorneoides*, *Dipteryx*

119 *oleifera*, and *Dalbergia retusa* as the basis for our analysis. *V. guatemalensis*, *H. alchorneoides*, *D.*

120 *oleifera*, and *D. retusa* are native to the area and have been suggested as promising native species for

121 timber plantations (Gamboa et al., 2015; González J., 2018). Teak (*T. grandis*) was included as it is

122 currently the most important plantation-grown species in Costa Rica.

123

124 2.1.1 Selected stands for optimization

125 For the CTN management optimization, we selected the four mixtures *H. alchorneoides*-*D. retusa*, *T.*

126 *grandis*-*D. oleifera*, *V. guatemalensis*-*D. oleifera*, and *V. guatemalensis*-*D. oleifera*-*D. retusa*. The

127 mixtures *T. grandis-D. oleifera*, *V. guatemalensis-D. oleifera*, and *V. guatemalensis-D. oleifera-D. retusa*
 128 were identified as mixtures of high economic and carbon sequestration potential on the site under
 129 even-aged management, while *H. alchorneoides-D. retusa* showed poor performance (Pinnschmidt et
 130 al., 2022). Table 1 shows the applied planting schemes. For the selected species we applied the Fertility
 131 Ratings model-fitted in Nölte et al. (2022) for the study site (Table 2). Fertility ratings are 3PG-specific
 132 relative measures for species-specific site productivity, corrected for climatic and soil water growth
 133 influences.

134 *Table 1 Planting schemes of the selected mixed-species stands*

Species combination	Initial planting density
	Trees/ha
<i>H. alchorneoides-D. retusa</i>	400-400
<i>T. grandis-D. oleifera</i>	400-400
<i>V. guatemalensis-D. oleifera</i>	400-400
<i>V. guatemalensis-D. oleifera-D. retusa</i>	400-200-200

135

136 *Table 2 Fertility ratings for the selected species on the study site*

Species	Fertility rating
<i>D. oleifera</i>	1.338
<i>D. retusa</i>	0.567
<i>H. alchorneoides</i>	0.478
<i>T. grandis</i>	1
<i>V. guatemalensis</i>	0.402

137

138 2.1.2 Selected CTN management practices

139 As outlined in the introduction, Close-to-Nature management can span a wide range of forest
 140 management practices that seek to mimic nature forest dynamics while minimizing negative ecological
 141 impacts for forest management interventions. For the purpose of this study, we consider *CTN forest*
 142 *management practices to be characterized by (1) the absence of large-scale clearcutting events, (2) the*

143 *use of multiple tree species, and/or (3) the maintenance of an uneven-aged stand structure. We*
144 *selected 4 CTN management practices to be included in the study. All four CTN management practices*
145 *were applied to mixed-species stands and incorporate at least one of the CTN forest management*
146 *characteristics defined above. Figure 2 Overview of key management intervention in mixed-species*
147 *stands managed according to CTN management practices illustrates key management interventions*
148 *during the harvesting and regeneration phase of the CTN management practices included in this study.*

149 First, we included even-aged management of the mixed-species stands as a CTN management practice
150 in the study. While even-aged management is generally not considered to be a CTN management
151 practice, the establishment of tropical mixed-species plantations (using native species) might itself be
152 considered an important step towards CTN conditions compared to conventional exotic-species
153 monoculture practices in tropical plantation forestry (Di Sacco et al., 2021).

154 Second, we included “*Retention Forestry*” as a CTN management practice. In retention forestry parts
155 of the forest stand (or individual trees) remain unmanaged or unharvested and are left to develop
156 according to natural forest dynamics. Meanwhile, the managed parts of the stand can be managed
157 according to conventional management practices. Accordingly, even-aged clear-cut harvesting can
158 take place on the managed stand sections while the retained forest patches offer important refuges
159 for forest species during and after such management interventions.

160 Third, we included “*Shelterwood Cutting*” as a CTN management practice. Shelterwood cutting is a
161 management practice in which a selected number of mature trees is left in the stand during final
162 harvesting as a “shelter” for the next generation of trees. Trees can be regenerated under this shelter
163 either by natural regeneration or underplanting. The shelter trees are removed once the new stand
164 has established itself. Shelterwood cutting practices hence avoid clear-cutting and bare-land
165 microclimatic conditions during the final harvesting and regeneration phase. While the stands are
166 uneven-aged during the regeneration phase, the stands are managed as even-aged stands once the
167 shelter trees are harvested.

168 Finally, we included “*Selective Harvesting*” as a CTN management practice. Under selective harvesting
 169 management, individual trees are harvested during harvesting interventions if they have reached
 170 maturity (e.g. a specified target size). Unmatured trees are left to continue growing. Regeneration of
 171 new trees takes place continuously to ensure a steady supply the mature trees. Selective harvesting
 172 results in an uneven-aged stand where no clear-cutting takes place.

173
 174 *Figure 2 Overview of key management intervention in mixed-species stands managed according to CTN management practices*

175
 176 **2.2 Forest economic model**

177 To optimize CTN management, we used the forest economic model published by Pinnschmidt et al.
 178 (2023, 2022). The model predicts forest growth using the process-based forest growth model 3PGmix
 179 (*Physiological Processes Predicting Growth*) and uses the growth outputs as the basis for its valuation
 180 modules for timber sales and the sale of carbon credits, and the cost module. 3PGmix estimates forest
 181 growth on a stand level by estimating the total amount of carbon fixed through photosynthesis under
 182 consideration of soil conditions, climate, and tree age. It is an extension of the 3PG model originally
 183 developed by Waring and Landsberg (1997). While 3PG only allowed for the simulation of monoculture
 184 stands, 3PGmix allows for vertical differentiation in the stand canopy, thereby allowing for the
 185 simulation of multilayered stands – i.e. mixed-species and uneven-aged stands (Forrester and Tang,
 186 2016). 3PGmix accounts for the different microclimates and shading that species (or cohorts) with

187 different canopy heights might experience by considering the vertical gradients in light availability,
188 aerodynamic conductance, vapor pressure deficit, and net radiation that occur in multi-layered stands.
189 Hereby, 3PGmix can represent aboveground species interaction effects and complementarity.
190 However, possible interaction effects related to soil nutrients are not represented. 3PGmix has been
191 used to model mixed-species and multi-layered forest stands under a wide variety of conditions
192 (Bouwman et al., 2021; Forrester et al., 2021; Forrester and Tang, 2016; Nölte et al., 2020; Trotsiuk et
193 al., 2020; Xu et al., 2022). For our study species, we applied the 3PGmix parameters published and
194 validated for the study site by Nölte et al. (2022). Based on the outputs of the 3PGmix model, the forest
195 economic model calculates the revenues that can be generated through the sale of timber, taking into
196 account key quality characteristics such as heartwood content and log diameter. Further, through the
197 extension of Pinnschmidt et al. (2023), the revenues that could be generated through the sale of
198 carbon credits are calculated. The model allows for the application of either
199 Afforestation/Reforestation (A/R) or Improved Forest Management (IFM) carbon credit accounting
200 methodologies. A/R carbon crediting methodologies are applied for new forest stands established on
201 former unforested land (e.g. abandoned pastures). Under this crediting scheme, carbon credits are
202 issued for the long-term additional CO₂ stored due to the reforestation activities (this is calculated
203 based on the mean carbon stored in the stand during the project period). IFM carbon credits can be
204 issued for existing forest stands if management changes are implemented that increase the long-term
205 CO₂ stored in the stand. Typical IFM management changes in plantation forest include extended
206 rotation times or maintaining higher stand densities. The amount of credits issued is calculated based
207 on the difference between the carbon stored under IFM management and the carbon that would have
208 been stored in the stand under “business-as-usual” management. For detail on the applied carbon
209 credits methodologies and associated costs see Pinnschmidt et al. (2023). Based on the generated
210 timber and/or carbon revenues, as well as the associated costs, economic performance indicators can
211 be calculated.

212

213 2.2.1 Integrating CTN management practices

214 So far, the forest economic model only allowed for even-aged management applying either age-based
 215 harvesting or harvesting based on reaching a species-specific target mean diameter at breast height
 216 (dbh). Replanting (or underplanting) only occurs when all trees of a species are removed from the
 217 simulated stand. To simulate CTN management practices we integrated alternative harvesting
 218 strategies, the possibility for continuous replanting/underplanting into the forest economic model, and
 219 the possibility of an uneven-aged stand structure. A detailed description of the integration of the CTN
 220 management options into the forest economic model can be found in Supplementary 1. We applied
 221 thinning based on basal area thresholds to all CTN management options.

222
 223 2.2.2 Biodiversity indicators

224 We further integrated 4 biodiversity indicators in the forest economic model following the
 225 recommendations of Blattert et al. (2017), namely *tree species diversity*, *structural diversity*, *deadwood*
 226 *volume*, and *presence of large (habitat) trees*. All indicators could be calculated directly from the
 227 model's forest growth outputs and can in practice be calculated from conventional forest inventory
 228 data (Table 3). The indicators represent important characteristics and preconditions for a species-rich
 229 forest ecosystem (Biber et al., 2020; Felton et al., 2017; Lindenmayer et al., 2012).

230 Table 3 Biodiversity indicators with equations

Biodiversity indicator		Equations	Description
Type	Indicator		
Tree species diversity	Shannon Index alpha diversity	$\overline{D.Species} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M D.Species_m}{M}$ Where: $H.Species_m = - \sum_{i=1}^S p_{i,m} \ln(p_{i,m})$ $D.Species_m = \exp(H.Species_m)$	Where $\overline{D.Species}$ is the mean tree species diversity of the modeling period, $D.species_m$ is the tree species alpha diversity based on the basal area by individual tree species occupied, m are individual monthly periods, M is the total number of monthly periods simulated, S is the number of tree species in

Structural diversity Post-hoc Index
alpha diversity

$$\overline{D.Struct} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M D.Struct_m}{M}$$

Where:

$$H.dbh_m = - \sum_{n=1}^{N.dbh} p_{n,m} \ln(p_{n,m})$$

$$H.h_m = - \sum_{k=1}^{N.h} p_{k,m} \ln(p_{k,m})$$

$$D.Struct_m = \exp\left(\frac{H.dbh_m + H.h_m}{2}\right)$$

the stand, $H.Species_m$ is the Shannon index, and p_i is the relative basal area share of species i in period m .

Where $\overline{D.Struct}$ is the mean stand vertical and horizontal structural diversity in the modeling period based on tree height and dbh, $D.Struct$ is the structural diversity in the monthly period m , $H.dbh_m$ and $H.h_m$ are the Shannon indices applied to the stands diameter and height classes respectively, $N.dbh$ and $N.h$ are the number of dbh and height classes, and $p_{n,m}$ and $p_{k,m}$ are the relative basal area in dbh and height class.

Deadwood volume Standing or lying deadwood volume

$$\overline{V.Dead} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{i=1}^S V.Dead_{i,m}}{M}$$

Where $\overline{V.Dead}$ is the mean volume of deadwood present in the stand during the modeling period, including harvest residues and $V.dead_{i,m}$ is the volume of species i in the monthly period m .

Presence of large (habitat) trees Min. 10 trees/ha of dbh > 40 cm

$$\overline{HT} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M HT_m}{M}$$

Where:

$$\begin{cases} HT_m = 1 & \text{if min. 10 trees with dbh} \geq 40 \\ HT_m = 0 & \text{if less 10 trees with dbh} \geq 40 \end{cases}$$

Where \overline{HT} is the proportion of time periods with at least 10 trees/ha of dbh > 40 cm and HT_m indicates the presence of more than 10 large trees per ha in monthly period m .

231

232 2.2.3 Economic and carbon sequestration performance

233 We used net present value (NPV) to measure the economic (i.e. financial) performance of the modeled

234 stands. NPV represents the sum of the discounted cash flows (which includes both revenues and costs)

235 for a specific period of time (Eq. 1). We calculated the NPV using a discount rate of 8% (Cubbage et al.,
236 2020, 2007).

$$237 \quad NPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{CF_t}{(1+r)^t} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

238 Where T is the end of the simulation periods (in years), CF_t is the cashflows (USD/ha) occurring in each
239 time t , and r is the discount rate.

240

241 To measure the carbon sequestration performance of the modeled stands we calculated the mean
242 carbon stored in living tree biomass (Schroeder, 1992) (Eq. 2).

$$243 \quad \overline{C.stand} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^M (C.stem_m + C.foli_m + C.root_m)}{M} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

244 Where $\overline{C.stand}$ is the modeled mean stand carbon stored in living trees at any point in time within
245 the planning period, m are individual monthly periods (the simulation model used simulates in monthly
246 intervals), M is the total number of monthly periods simulated, $C.stem_m$, $C.foli_m$, and $C.root_m$ is the
247 carbon stored in living tree stems, foliage, and roots in the individual monthly period.

248

249 2.3 Optimization

250 We assumed that the objective of commercial plantations is to maximize profitability. Accordingly, we
251 aimed to optimize the management parameters to maximize the NPV of the modeled monoculture
252 and CTN-managed stands (Eq. 3).

$$253 \quad \max\{NPV_{BA1, BA2, HP, RS}\} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

254 Where NPV is the NPV of the modeled stand, $BA1$ is the applied upper basal area threshold to initiate
255 thinning, $BA2$ is the applied target basal area after thinning, HP are the applied harvesting parameters
256 further specified for each CTN management practice in Supplementary 1, and RS is the applied relative
257 spacing threshold for underplanting.

258

259 We applied two stand establishment scenarios. In the first scenario, the modeled stands established
260 on bare land (i.e. unforested land such as former pastures). In the second scenario, mature
261 monoculture stands were transformed into mixed-species CTN-managed plantations. For each
262 mixture, we selected the species in the mixtures that showed the highest economic potential on the
263 study site when grown as a monoculture to be the baseline for the stand transformation. Hence, the
264 mixtures *T. grandis-D.oleifera*, *V. guatemalensis-D. oleifera*, and *V. guatemalensis-D. oleifera-D. retusa*
265 were established by transforming a mature *D. oleifera* monoculture, while the mixture *H.*
266 *alchorneoides-D. retusa* was established by transforming a mature *D. retusa* monoculture (Pinnschmidt
267 et al., 2023).

268 We also applied two valuation scenarios. In the first scenario, we only considered revenues from
269 timber sales. In the second scenario, we also included revenues from carbon credits in the stand
270 valuation. For stands established from bare land, we used the Afforestation/Reforestation (A/F) carbon
271 crediting methodology, while for stands established by transforming mature monocultures, we used
272 the Improved Forest Management (IFM) methodology (Pinnschmidt et al., 2023). We considered
273 carbon credit prices of 10, 50, and 100 USD/tCO_{2e}.

274 To optimize the management parameters for each scenario and maximize NPV, we used a genetic
275 optimization algorithm based on Differential Evolution (Mullen et al., 2011). To ensure that the
276 modeled CTN stands managed using shelterwood cutting or selective harvesting did not undergo clear
277 cutting, we implemented a penalty constraint that required the average distance between trees to be
278 no more than 1 tree length. We maximized NPV for a planning period of 80 years (i.e. 2020-2100).

279

280 We compared the performance of the optimize CTN managed stands against the performance of even-
281 aged monoculture stands of the 5 study species. The management of the even-aged monoculture
282 stands was optimized to maximize NPV in the same way as described for the CTN managed stands
283 described above.

284

285 2.4 Opportunity costs and sensitivity analysis

286 To assess the commercial competitiveness of tropical CTN-managed plantations, we calculated the
287 opportunity costs of applying CTN management practices. Opportunity costs were calculated by
288 subtracting the NPV of optimized CTN-managed stands from the NPV of monoculture stands under
289 optimized management. The CTN-managed stands were compared against the best-performing
290 species grown as a monoculture of the respective stands. From the opportunity costs, we calculated
291 the changes in costs or timber revenues needed for the CTN-managed stands to break even with the
292 best-performing monocultures (i.e. to reach an opportunity cost of 0). Finally, we calculated the carbon
293 credits price and annual biodiversity payments required for the CTN-managed stands to break even.
294 These biodiversity payments can be thought of as hypothetical annual easement payments covering
295 the opportunity costs of implementing CTN management practices.

296

297 3. Results

298 In this study, we compared the economic potential, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity potential
299 of Close-to-Nature managed plantations to conventional monoculture plantations on a study site in
300 Central America. We also evaluated the impact of carbon payments on the economic performance of
301 CTN-managed plantations. The study examined two establishment scenarios: reforestation on bare
302 land and transformation of mature monoculture stands.

303

304 3.1 Economic potential of CTN management

305
 306 Figure 3 The economic potential of CTN-managed plantations evaluated based on two establishment scenarios: (A)
 307 reforestation of bare land and (B) transformation of mature even-aged monoculture plantations. In the "Timber" valuation
 308 scenario, only revenues from timber sales were considered. In the "pC10", "pC50", and "pC100" scenarios, payments for carbon
 309 credits were also included in the valuation at prices of 10, 50, and 100 USD/tCO₂e, respectively. The colored lines in the figure
 310 represent the economic potential of even-aged monoculture plantations under optimized management.

311
 312 First, we examined the economic potential of CTN-managed plantations established either on bare
 313 land or by transforming mature even-aged monoculture plantations. Figure 3 presents the economic
 314 potential of CTN-managed plantations under optimized management. The optimized management
 315 parameters can be found in Supplementary 2. When only revenues from timber sales were considered
 316 in the valuation, all CTN management types were economically viable on the study site for the mixtures
 317 *T. grandis-D. oleifera* (3073-4016 USD/ha), *V. guatemalensis-D. oleifera* (3225-4827 USD/ha), and *V.*
 318 *guatemalensis-D. oleifera-D. retusa* (2597-3952 USD/ha) at a discount rate of 8% when plantations
 319 were established on bare land. The mixture *H. alchorneoides-D. retusa* was not economically viable
 320 under any management type. Mixed stands managed under even-aged management had the highest
 321 economic potential across all mixtures, while stands managed through selective harvesting had the
 322 lowest economic potential. The even-aged managed and shelterwood-managed stand *V.*

323 *guatemalensis-D. oleifera* (4827 and 4694 USD/ha) had a higher economic performance than the best-
 324 performing optimized monoculture plantation (*D. oleifera*: 4237 USD/ha) on the site.

325 When CTN-managed plantations were established by transforming mature monoculture stands, all
 326 CTN management strategies were economically viable for all mixtures when considering only revenues
 327 from timber sales in the valuation. Again, even-aged managed mixtures had the highest economic
 328 potential while selective harvesting had the poorest performance.

329 Including carbon payments in the valuation significantly increased the economic potential of CTN-
 330 managed plantations established on bare land or by transforming mature monoculture stands. The
 331 improvements in economic potential ranged from 0-1009 USD/ha, 621-8194 USD/ha, and 2297-17478
 332 USD/ha at carbon prices of 10, 50, and 100 USD/tCO₂e, respectively.

333 The CTN-managed stands did not outperform the best-performing monocultures financially if the
 334 monocultures also received carbon payments but also never performed poorer than the worst-
 335 performing comparison monoculture stand (except CTN-managed *H. alchorneoides-D. retusa*). If
 336 monocultures were excluded from receiving carbon payments, most CTN-managed stands
 337 outperformed the best-performing monocultures at carbon prices above 50 USD/tCO₂e regardless of
 338 the initial stand scenario (see Supplementary 2).

339

340 3.2 Carbon sequestration and biodiversity potential

341

342 *Figure 4 Mean stand carbon stored in living trees by (A) reforesting bare land or (B) transforming mature even-aged*
343 *monoculture plantations. In the "Timber" valuation scenario, only revenues from timber sales were taken into account. In the*
344 *"pC10," "pC50," and "pC100" valuation scenarios, payments for carbon credits were also included at carbon prices of 10, 50,*
345 *and 100 USD/tCO_{2e}, respectively. The colored lines show the carbon storage potential of even-aged monoculture plantations.*

346

347 Carbon storage in CTN-managed stands was generally similar to that of conventional even-aged
348 monoculture stands (ranging from 23.6 to 63.6 tons C per hectare) when CTN-managed stands were
349 solely managed for timber sales (Figure 4). Stands managed through selective harvesting showed the
350 lowest carbon storage of the CTN-managed stands when the plantations were established on bare
351 land, while even-aged mixtures showed the lowest carbon storage when CTN stands were established
352 through the transformation of a mature monoculture. The inclusion of carbon payments in the
353 valuation resulted in consistently increasing carbon storage with increasing carbon prices. At a carbon
354 price of 100 USD/tCO_{2e}, carbon storage in CTN-managed stands increased by up to 8.6% to 97.9%
355 compared to stands solely managed for timber sales.

356 The carbon storage in CTN-managed stands established on bare land and those established by
357 transforming mature monocultures were largely similar. Thus, establishing CTN-managed stands on
358 bare land or land with relatively low above-ground biomass, such as pastures, would result in a
359 considerably larger net climate benefit through carbon sequestration compared to transforming
360 mature monocultures. In fact, under optimized management, the transformation of mature
361 monocultures to CTN-managed stands only resulted in increased carbon storage when the stands
362 received carbon payments (i.e. CTN stands solely managed for timber sales did not consistently achieve
363 increased carbon storage compared to monocultures).

364 Regardless of the initial stand scenario, CTN-managed stands only consistently achieved increased
365 carbon storage compared to monoculture stands when monoculture stands did not receive carbon
366 payments (see Supplementary 2). Modeled *D. oleifera* monocultures partly achieve a considerable

367 higher carbon storage than the comparison CTN-managed stands when carbon payments were
 368 included in the valuation.
 369

370
 371 *Figure 5 Key biodiversity indicators of CTN-managed plantations established by reforesting bare land. In valuation scenario*
 372 *"Timber" only revenues from timber sales were considered in the valuation In the "Timber" valuation scenario, only revenues*
 373 *from timber sales were taken into account. In the "pC10," "pC50," and "pC100" valuation scenarios, payments for carbon*
 374 *credits were also included at carbon prices of 10, 50, and 100 USD/tCO₂e, respectively. The colored lines show the*
 375 *biodiversity potential of even-aged monoculture plantations.*

376
 377 Figure 5 presents biodiversity indicator values for CTN-managed plantations established on bare land.
 378 Biodiversity indicator values for CTN-managed plantations established by transforming mature
 379 monocultures can be found in Supplementary 2 (but are largely similar). Overall, CTN-managed
 380 plantations exhibited higher biodiversity indicator values compared to monoculture plantations for

381 indicators of structural diversity, species diversity, and partially for the presence of large trees (expect
382 when compared with monocultures of *V. guatemalensis* at high carbon prices). In contrast, biodiversity
383 indicator values for deadwood volume and partially for the presence of large trees were within the
384 range of values modeled in monoculture plantations. Even-aged mixed-species stands and
385 shelterwood stands generally had the lowest values for structural diversity and species diversity among
386 CTN-managed plantations.

387

388 There was no clear or consistent effect of carbon payments or increasing carbon prices on the
389 biodiversity indicators. These effects appeared to be highly stand-specific, meaning they were specific
390 to individual species combinations and management strategies. The only consistent trend was an
391 increase in the presence of large trees with increasing carbon prices for CTN stands managed through
392 selective harvesting. In some cases, the biodiversity indicators showed hints of a downward concave
393 curve with increasing carbon prices, such as for all biodiversity indicators for *V. guatemalensis-D.*
394 *oleifera* (especially under retention forestry or even-aged management) or the structural diversity of
395 *T. grandis-D. oleifera*. This suggests that in specific cases biodiversity indicators may initially increase
396 with the inclusion of carbon payments and increasing carbon prices under optimized management, but
397 decrease once a certain carbon price threshold is exceeded.

398

399 3.3 Breaking even with conventional monocultures

400
 401 *Figure 6 Opportunity costs of establishing CTN-managed plantations compared to the best performing monocultures*
 402 *considering only revenues from timber sales in the valuation. The transformation scenarios consider CTN-managed plantations*
 403 *established by reforesting bare land (“Bare land”) or transforming mature even-aged monoculture plantations (“Mono”). D.*
 404 *olei, D. retu, H. alch, T. gran, and V. guat refers to the species D. oleifera, D. retusa, H. alchorneoides, T. grandis, and V.*
 405 *guatemalensis respectively*
 406 As shown previously, CTN-managed plantations generally had lower economic potential compared to
 407 the best-performing monocultures, when only considering revenues from timber sales in the valuation.
 408 The opportunity cost of establishing CTN plantations, or the difference in economic potential between
 409 CTN plantations and monocultures, was higher when transforming mature monocultures (1577
 410 USD/ha on average) than when establishing CTN plantations on bare land (485 USD/ha on average)
 411 (see Figure 6). Mixed-species stands managed under even-aged management had the lowest
 412 opportunity cost in both scenarios, while stands managed through selective harvesting had the highest
 413 opportunity cost. However, in a few instances (e.g. *H. alchorneoides-D. retusa* and *V. guatemalensis-*

414 *D. oleifera* under even-aged and shelterwood management), mixtures had a marginally higher NPV
 415 than the best-performing monocultures, resulting in negative opportunity costs.
 416

417
 418 *Figure 7* Total costs reduction (A) or timber revenue increase (B) necessary for CTN-managed plantations to break even with
 419 the best performing even-aged monocultures. The transformation scenarios consider CTN-managed plantations established
 420 by reforesting bare land ("Bare land") or transforming mature even-aged monoculture plantations ("Mono"). *D. olei*, *D. retu*,
 421 *H. alch*, *T. gran*, and *V. guat* refers to the species *D. oleifera*, *D. retusa*, *H. alchorneoides*, *T. grandis*, and *V. guatemalensis*
 422 respectively

423
 424 To compensate for the opportunity costs of CTN plantations, total discounted costs would need to be
 425 reduced by 5% to 33.1% for CTN plantations on bare land or 1.6% to 104.2% for CTN plantations
 426 transformed from mature monocultures (excluding CTN-managed stands that achieved negative
 427 opportunity costs) (Figure 7). If only planting costs were reduced (e.g. through using natural
 428 regeneration), planting costs would need to be reduced by 70.3% to 930.4% (see Supplementary 2).
 429 Even-aged mixtures would require the lowest cost reductions to break even with monocultures, while
 430 stands managed through selective harvesting would require the largest reductions (in some cases
 431 above 100%). Timber revenue would need to be increased by 3% to 38.9% for CTN plantations

432 established on bare land or 0.3% to 23.1% for CTN plantations transformed from mature monocultures
 433 (including timber revenues of the mature monocultures).
 434

435
 436 *Figure 8 Carbon price (A) and yearly biodiversity payments (B) necessary for CTN-managed plantations to break even with the*
 437 *best performing even-aged monocultures if monocultures were excluded from carbon payment schemes. The transformation*
 438 *scenarios consider CTN-managed plantations established by reforesting bare land ("Bare land") or transforming mature even-*
 439 *aged monoculture plantations ("Mono"). D. olei, D. retu, H. alch, T. gran, and V. quat refers to the species D. oleifera, D. retusa,*
 440 *H. alchorneoides, T. grandis, and V. guatemalensis respectively*

441
 442 When considering carbon credits in the valuation and management optimization, CTN plantations
 443 would break even with monocultures at carbon prices ranging from 2.2 to 21.9 USD/tCO₂e for CTN
 444 plantations established on bare land or 2 to 49.3 USD/tCO₂e for CTN plantations transformed from
 445 mature monocultures (estimated through linear interpolation, excluding CTN-managed stands that
 446 achieved negative opportunity costs), assuming monocultures do not receive carbon credits (Figure 8).
 447 As before, even-aged mixtures would require the lowest carbon prices to break even with
 448 monocultures, while stands managed through selective harvesting would require the highest carbon
 449 prices. Additionally, annual "biodiversity payments" of 19.6 to 145.5 USD/ha for CTN plantations

450 established on bare land or 4.5 to 308.2 USD/ha for CTN plantations transformed from mature
451 monocultures would be necessary for CTN plantations to break even with the best-performing
452 monocultures.

453

454 4. Discussion

455 In this study, we aimed to evaluate the economic feasibility of Close-to-Nature management of tropical
456 timber plantations in comparison to conventional monoculture plantations. We also examined the
457 potential for carbon payments to fund CTN management practices and the possibility for CTN
458 management to provide additional carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits alongside timber
459 production.

460

461 4.1 Economic potential of tropical Close-to-Nature plantations

462 We found that CTN management of tropical timber plantations was economically viable when only
463 considering revenues from timber sales in the valuation. The best economic potential was achieved
464 through even-aged management of mixed-species stands, with the performance of a given stand highly
465 dependent on the selection of suitable tree species. *H. alchorneoides* and *D. retusa* were not
466 commercially viable on the study site, and their mixture was not economically viable under any
467 management type when established on bare land (as was already suggested earlier by Pinnschmidt et
468 al. (2022)). The inclusion of carbon payments substantially increased the economic potential of CTN-
469 managed plantations, with the improvements ranging from 0-1009 USD/ha to 2297-17478 USD/ha at
470 carbon prices of 10 and 100 USD/ha, respectively. At carbon prices above 50 USD/ha, most CTN-
471 managed stands outperformed the best-performing monoculture plantations if these monocultures
472 did not receive carbon payments. Monoculture reforestations might increasingly not qualify for carbon
473 credits as carbon certification schemes increasingly require reforestation projects to produce benefits
474 beyond carbon storage, such as biodiversity conservation (Gold Standard, 2019; VERRA, 2017).
475 However, if the monoculture plantations also received carbon payments, CTN-managed plantations

476 did not consistently outperform them. These findings extend to previous studies that had already
477 suggested that timber plantations of native species monocultures and even-aged mixed-species
478 plantations could be financially viable in the tropics (Griess and Knoke, 2011; Pinnschmidt et al., 2023,
479 2022; Piotta et al., 2010; Sinacore et al., 2022; Streed et al., 2006).

480 The transformation from mature monoculture stands to mixed-species CTN managed plantations was
481 associated to high opportunity costs for most of the CTN practices and mixtures. High transformation
482 costs at high discount rates were also reported by Nölte et al. (2018), who analyzed the transformation
483 of even-aged into uneven-aged teak plantations. They also found transformation costs increased along
484 with structural diversity. When establishing CTN mixed-species stands on bare land, we observed lower
485 opportunity costs compared to transformation from mature monocultures, or in some cases even
486 negative opportunity costs. This aligns with findings from Nölte et al. (2018), who reported uneven-
487 aged forest management to be economically attractive once the transformation was completed, and
488 with the results of previous economic studies in temperate forests (Knoke, 2012; Vítková et al., 2021).
489 The higher opportunity cost of transforming a mature monoculture is due to the opportunity cost of
490 forgone revenues from postponing the harvesting of the mature stand, taking into account the time
491 value of money. Among the CTN management practices, the highest opportunity costs of
492 transformation were observed in practices that do not allow clear-cutting or that involve harvesting in
493 intervals, such as selective harvesting. When using the best-performing monoculture as a baseline for
494 comparison, the opportunity costs may also include the admixture of species with lower economic
495 potential (e.g. when admixing *D. retusa*, which does not appear to be a commercially viable species on
496 the study site).

497

498 4.2 Carbon and biodiversity benefits

499 When solely managed for timber production, CTN-managed plantations had similar carbon storage
500 levels to even-aged monoculture plantations, regardless whether established on bare land or by
501 transforming mature monoculture stands. Biodiversity indicator values were generally higher in CTN-

502 managed plantations compared to monoculture plantations in terms of structural diversity and species
503 diversity, but were similar or lower in terms of deadwood volume and the presence of large trees.
504 Thus, CTN practices could be important for increasing the biodiversity value of forest plantations, but
505 not necessarily for enhancing its carbon storage potential.

506 A significant increase in carbon storage was achieved by an increase in carbon prices. Current carbon
507 prices could not significantly increase the carbon storage potential, as was reported previously
508 (Derwisch et al., 2009; Nölte et al., 2018). However, with carbon prices above 50 USD/tCO₂e carbon
509 storage approximately doubled for some of the mixtures and CTN practices. The effects of carbon
510 payments on biodiversity indicators were stand-specific and not consistent, showing that carbon
511 storage and biodiversity protection do not always align and that the creation of performance-based
512 biodiversity payments, or the exclusion of monocultures from current carbon certification schemes,
513 might be necessary in order to explicitly incentivize biodiversity protection in plantation forestry.

514 According to previous research, mixed-species stands might be more suitable for carbon plantings than
515 monoculture plantations due to the presence of complementary interaction effects (Hulvey et al.,
516 2013; Le et al., 2020; Schnabel et al., 2019). However, a recent simulation study by Pinnschmidt et al.
517 (2023) found that tropical mixed-species plantations managed using even-aged techniques did not
518 consistently show higher or lower carbon storage compared to monoculture plantations managed to
519 maximize carbon sequestration. This finding also applies to the other CTN management practices
520 studied in this study. The lack of carbon outperformance in mixed-species stands may be partly due to
521 the limitations of the 3PGmix model, which can represent species-interaction effects related to
522 competition for light, but not facilitative species-interaction effects. Additionally, the results of this
523 study do not consider the ability of mixed-species stands to buffer against interannual productivity
524 variations (Schnabel et al., 2021). It is important to note that studies exploring theoveryielding effect
525 of mixed-species stands often involve high-density research plots or natural forests. In commercial
526 timber plantations, regardless of whether they are managed using conventional monoculture even-
527 aged techniques or mixed-species CTN management, stand density is often reduced to promote

528 individual tree growth in order to achieve shorter rotation times. This reduction in stand density may
529 also weaken species interaction effects (Mina et al., 2018).

530 CTN-managed stands showed increased species and structural diversity compared to monoculture
531 plantations, but not in terms of deadwood volume or the presence of large trees. The deadwood in
532 this study consisted mainly of harvest residues and was therefore closely related to stand productivity.

533 Even-aged mixed-species stands had the lowest species and structural diversity among CTN-managed
534 stands but showed higher or equivalent biodiversity indicator values compared to monoculture
535 plantations. These findings suggest that the adoption of mixed-species practices, including even-aged
536 management, can increase biodiversity in plantation forests and that continuous cover practices such
537 as shelterwood cutting, selective harvesting, or retention forestry may further benefit biodiversity
538 (Lindenmayer et al., 2003; Stephens and Wagner, 2007). There was no consistent relationship between
539 the inclusion of carbon payments in the valuation and management optimization and the biodiversity
540 indicator values. Accordingly, optimizing stand management to increase payments for carbon credits
541 does not necessarily lead to improved biodiversity values. The only consistent trend was an increase
542 in the presence of large trees with increasing carbon prices. Under optimized management, increasing
543 carbon prices often leads to increased rotation times, i.e. larger tree sizes at harvesting (Hou et al.,
544 2020; Quintero-Méndez and Jerez-Rico, 2019).

545

546 Carbon storage and biodiversity are important arguments for the adoption of CTN management
547 practices. However, our study did not consider several other benefits of these practices. Mixed-species
548 forestry has been demonstrated to reduce financial risk in managed forests through various
549 mechanisms, including the stabilization of growth resulting from mixing tree species, a reduced
550 likelihood of large-scale disasters, and the production of multiple timber products, which can mitigate
551 market-related risk (Knoke et al., 2008; Messier et al., 2021; Nichols et al., 2006). Additionally, some
552 CTN management strategies, such as selective harvesting, may further reduce market-related risks

553 through risk spreading due to more frequent harvesting interventions (though the amount of
554 harvested wood at each intervention is smaller) (Knoke, 2012; Pukkala, 2015; Roessiger et al., 2011).

555

556 4.3 Modeling assumptions, limitations, and uncertainties

557 There are several limitations and uncertainties to consider when interpreting the results of this study
558 on the economic, carbon, and biodiversity potential of tropical Close-to-Nature timber plantations.

559

560 First, the study is based on simulations rather than real-world examples. While simulations can be
561 useful, real-world examples of tropical CTN-managed plantations are necessary to confirm the validity
562 of the results and to understand their broader applicability. To date, such examples of real-world CTN-
563 managed plantations are lacking in the tropics (except even-aged, mixed-species plantations).
564 Nonetheless, the 3PGmix forest growth model underlying our simulations has been tested extensively
565 – and shown good predictive abilities – for a wide variety of mixed-species and uneven-aged forest
566 stands around the world (e.g. Forrester et al. (2021); Forrester and Tang (2016); Nölte et al. (2022)).

567 Second, the study found that selective harvesting performed poorly compared to other CTN
568 management strategies. This result is in contrast to the broader literature, which often suggests that
569 selective harvesting can be more effective than even-aged stands because individual trees can be
570 harvested closer to their economic optimum (Hanewinkel et al., 2014; Pukkala, 2015). The 3PGmix
571 model used in this study assumes a homogenous stand (i.e. tree of different species or cohorts are
572 spread evenly across space) and does not model gaps that would be present in a real-world selective
573 harvesting system. In practice, replanting or natural regeneration would most likely occur in the gaps
574 left by felled trees rather than being evenly distributed throughout the stand. Additionally, in a
575 heterogenous stand, a higher stand density and larger target diameters may be maintained, which
576 could lead to higher productivity and better economic performance. Despite this limitation, the study
577 highlights the potential of selective harvesting practices for improving biodiversity, for example by
578 achieving a high structural diversity.

579 Third, we compared the economic potential of CTN-managed plantations and monocultures assuming
580 that both were managed to their full economic potential. In reality, there may be fewer management
581 recommendations (or none) available for CTN-managed plantations, and monocultures may be more
582 likely to be managed optimally. This means that the opportunity costs of CTN-managed stands may be
583 even higher in practice than what is reflected in this study. It should here be noted, that CTN-managed
584 stands were assessed against the best-performing monocultures. This allowed for a conservative
585 economic assessment, but it may also be too restrictive. For example, in the study region, teak
586 plantations are the most common plantations (REDD/CCAD-GIZ-SINAC, 2015). If teak monocultures
587 had been taken as the baseline for assessment on the specific study site, the admixing of *D. oleifera*
588 would have resulted in negative opportunity costs (i.e. would be profitable) under several CTN
589 management scenarios.

590 Finally, the study assumed that the same management costs and timber prices would apply to both
591 CTN-managed plantations and monocultures. However, the costs of CTN plantations may differ due to
592 the increased complexity of the management, which may require more work and the maintenance of
593 a highly skilled crew. In uneven-aged stands, smaller trees may be damaged during the harvesting of
594 larger trees, which could lead to the loss of trees or reduced timber quality and price. Increased costs
595 and reduced revenues would, again, lead to increased opportunity costs for CTN management.

596
597 Clearly, the CTN management practices considered in this study and the resulting modeled stands still
598 represent strongly simplified forest ecosystems compared to natural tropical forests where tens - or
599 even hundreds - of tree species can co-exist in close vicinity (Gillespie et al., 2009; Lieberman et al.,
600 1996). Nonetheless, they offer a seemingly financially viable and ecologically valuable alternative to
601 conventional even-aged monoculture plantations that can be managed based on relatively simple
602 management heuristics. In the broader trend towards multi-purpose forest management that has also
603 reached tropical plantation forestry, CTN managed plantations might be an important component of

604 future tropical forest landscapes within the sparing-sharing continuum (Betts et al., 2021; Jones et al.,
605 2023; Runting et al., 2019).

606

607 4.4 Making Close-to-Nature plantations competitive

608 Currently, investors would likely incur an opportunity cost by applying CTN management, due to
609 reduced economic performance and increased risk from the lack of management experience and
610 increased management complexity. However, while some CTN management practices may not
611 currently be competitive with the best-performing monocultures, they may still be economically viable
612 on their own. They may therefore already be an option for forest investors who have investment
613 objectives beyond profit maximization. Continuous cover management practices may also already be
614 applied and economically viable in areas where frequent clear-cutting is not desirable.

615 The competitiveness of CTN-managed stands could be improved by using natural regeneration, which
616 reduces planting costs compared to monocultures that are commonly planted. In the tropics, using
617 natural regeneration may reduce the cost of regeneration by 70% compared to planting (Nunes et al.,
618 2020; Shono et al., 2007). However, in this study, even a planting cost reduction of 100% did not cover
619 opportunity costs in several instances and does not seem like a promising driver of CTN
620 competitiveness.

621 It could be speculated that timber from CTN plantations can be marketed as "more sustainable" and
622 achieve a price premium compared to timber from conventional plantations. However, evidence of
623 price premiums for sustainable timber is sporadic and rarely exceeds the additional costs for
624 certification and marketing that may occur (Chen et al., 2010; Ebeling and Yasué, 2009; Espach, 2006;
625 Nebel et al., 2005).

626

627 Recently, carbon prices for carbon credits from reforestation projects reached 3-12 USD/tCO₂e on the
628 voluntary carbon market (Forest Trends' Ecosystem Marketplace, 2021). At these prices, carbon
629 payments for CTN-managed plantations could cover opportunity costs on the study site, if

630 monocultures are excluded from carbon payments, for plantations established on bare land. Carbon
631 prices are projected to exceed 100 USD/tCO₂e in the future (Credit Suisse, 2022; The World Bank,
632 2022; Trove Research, 2021). At this price, even the transformation of existing mature monocultures
633 to CTN-managed mixed-species stands would be financially feasible, if such transformation qualifies
634 the transformed stands for receiving carbon credits from Improved Forest Management (IFM) carbon
635 crediting schemes. However, under current certification schemes, the establishment of exotic species
636 monocultures qualify for carbon credits (if “additionality” can be demonstrated), which may present a
637 barrier to the widespread adoption of CTN management practices in tropical timber plantations.
638 Currently, performance-based biodiversity credit schemes are being developed (World Economic
639 Forum, 2022). Under these schemes, the restoration of key ecosystem characteristics and functions is
640 rewarded with biodiversity credits that can be sold on international (voluntary) markets, similar to
641 carbon credits (Wallacea Trust, 2022). Based on the results of this study, the explicit remuneration of
642 biodiversity benefits would likely favor the establishment of CTN-managed plantations, even if
643 monocultures are also included in such certification schemes, as CTN-managed stands generally
644 showed higher or equivalent biodiversity indicator values. The relation between carbon credit and
645 biodiversity credit prices may then become a key driver for the competitiveness of CTN-managed
646 plantations.

647

648 5. Conclusion

649 Overall, this study found that CTN management practices might be an economically viable alternative
650 to current monoculture practices in tropical plantations forests under appropriate site and tree species
651 selection. The application of CTN management practices could also produce considerable biodiversity
652 benefits by increasing the structural and tree species diversity of tropical timber plantations. At current
653 carbon prices, CTN-managed plantations might be financially competitive with monocultures if
654 monoculture practices are excluded from carbon certification schemes. If carbon prices increase
655 further, the sale of IFM-based carbon credits could finance the transformation of existing monoculture

656 stands to mixed-species CTN-managed stands. The implementation of performance-based biodiversity
657 crediting and payments could further improve the competitiveness of CTN management practices in
658 tropical plantation forestry.

659

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663

664 Conflict of interest

665 The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

666

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913

Preprint

915 Supplementary 1 – Methodology

916

917 I. Integrating Close-to-Nature management options

918 To simulate CTN management practices we integrated alternative harvesting strategies, the
919 possibility for continuous replanting/underplanting into the forest economic model, and the
920 possibility of an uneven-aged stand structure.

921

922 Forest patch retention

923 We integrated the retention of forest patches – to facilitate the simulation of retention forestry
924 patches – by dividing the simulated stand into two sections. One section – the retention section – is
925 simulated without any thinning or harvesting interventions. The other section – the managed section
926 – is managed according to even-aged management practices. The size of the retained forest patches is
927 determined by an *area retained (%)* parameter. Following the growth simulations, the growth outputs
928 of the retained and the managed stand sections are merged and then corrected to 1 ha. It is important
929 to note that this modeling approach assumes that there are no interactions or edge-effects between
930 the retained and the managed stand sections. As 3PGmix assumes that the modeled trees are
931 distributed homogeneously across the stand, group-wise growth simulations cannot be simulated
932 within a single simulation but need to be divided into multiple simulation runs (Nölte et al., 2018).

933

934 Shelterwood Cutting

935 To facilitate shelterwood cutting the tree species are harvested when a species-specific target mean
936 dbh is reached (as under the conventional even-aged management applied in (Pinnschmidt et al.,
937 2022)). When only one tree species remains in the stands, reaching the target mean dbh initiates the
938 shelterwood cutting sequence where (1) a specified proportion of the trees are harvested while some
939 trees remain in the stand; (2) the next generation of trees is underplanted under the remaining trees;
940 (3) after a specified amount of time the remaining mature trees are harvested. The proportion of trees

941 remaining as shelterwood is determined by a *shelterwood basal area* parameter while the time
942 between the shelterwood cutting and the harvesting of the remaining trees is determined by a
943 *shelterwood time* parameter. We assumed the trees remaining after the shelterwood cutting are
944 randomly selected. From a 3PGmix modeling perspective, the shelterwood cutting hence equals a
945 cross-sectional thinning with a biomass fraction of the removed trees of 1.

946

947 Selective Harvesting

948 To integrate selective harvesting we assumed that harvesting interventions take place in regular time
949 intervals. During the harvesting intervention, individual trees that exceed a specified species-specific
950 target dbh are harvested while trees below this threshold remain in the stand. In practice, we
951 implemented the selective harvesting intervention as a special case of a “thinning from above”
952 intervention (Pinnschmidt et al., 2022). The number of trees harvested during the harvesting
953 interventions (and their biomass) was determined by extracting the dbh Weibull distribution at the
954 time of the harvesting intervention. In 3PGmix, harvesting and thinning are performed by specifying
955 the number of stems removed during the harvest intervention and the applied “thinning fraction”. The
956 thinning fractions refer to the mean tree biomass of the harvested trees in relation to the mean tree
957 biomass of the stand before removing the harvested trees. During clear-cut harvesting, the thinning
958 fraction hence equals 1, as all trees are removed. During selective harvesting by target diameter
959 harvesting, thinning fractions will be above 1, as the larger trees of the stand are removed. In practice,
960 it resembles a thinning from above. Based on the dbh classes of the dbh Weibull distribution we
961 calculated the associated stem biomass for each dbh class using Eq. S1.1 (Forrester, 2020):

$$962 \quad w_s = a_s DBH^{n_s} \quad (\text{Eq. S1.1})$$

963 Where w_s is the mean stem and branch biomass, DBH is the mean stem diameter at breast height
964 (dbh), and a_s and n_s coefficients and exponents fitted in Nölte et al. (2022) as part of the 3PG
965 parametrization.

966

967 We then calculated the stem thinning fraction for each dbh class using the cumulative probability
 968 density. So far, the calculation of the thinning fractions assumed that selective harvesting exclusively
 969 harvests trees above the target diameter. To allow for the possibility that a few trees above the target
 970 diameter remain in the stands, while a few trees below the target diameter are harvested, we added
 971 $\frac{1}{4}$ of the distance between the initially calculated thinning fraction and 1. We also used the stem
 972 thinning fraction for the root and foliage thinning fractions.

973
 974 To apply the selective harvesting practice, the stand should already show an uneven-aged stand
 975 structure. For even-aged stands we, therefore, applied a predetermined transformation sequence, i.e.
 976 thinning and harvesting sequence. The mixture-specific sequences can be found Table S1.1.

977 *Table S1.1 Thinning and harvesting schedule to transform even-aged mixtures into mixtures that can be harvested using*
 978 *selective harvesting. Underplanting may take place after each intervention after each thinning or harvesting intervention.*

Mixture ⁱ	Thinnings ⁱⁱ					Harvesting age	
	Sp.1	Sp.1	Sp. 2	Sp.2	Sp. 2	Sp.1	Sp.2
Sp.1-Sp.2-Sp.3							
	<i>Age (stems remaining per ha)</i>						
<i>T. gran-D. olei</i>	8 (200)	12 (50)	8 (300)	12 (250)	15 (150)	15	
<i>V. guat-D. olei</i>	4 (150)	6 (50)	12 (250)	15 (150)		8	
<i>V. guat-D. olei-D. retu</i>	4 (150)	6 (50)	12 (150)			8	25
<i>H. alch-D. retu</i>	8 (200)	12 (50)				15	

979 (i) *D. olei*, *D. retu*, *H. alch*, *T. gran*, and *V. guat* refer to the species *D. oleifera*, *D. retusa*, *H. alchorneoides*, *T. grandis*, and *V.*
 980 *guatemalensis* respectively; (ii) Age-based thinning schedules consist of a thinning age (the first number in each cell) and a
 981 target stem number after thinning, here given in brackets. Missing values indicate no thinning.

982 983 Continuous underplanting

984 In 3PGmix stands are regenerated through planting. In the forest economic model of Pinnschmidt et
 985 al. (2022) replanting or underplanting only takes place once all trees of a species are removed from
 986 the stand. We implemented the option for continuous underplanting to facilitate uneven-aged
 987 management. To do so, the option underplant is evaluated following ever thinning or harvesting

988 intervention based on the relative spacing (RS) of the remaining stand. Relative spacing is a measure
989 of stand density and was calculated as the relation between the modeled stand area and the squared
990 mean stand tree height (Eq. S1.2) (Pinnschmidt et al., 2022; Pretzsch, 2019).

$$991 \quad RS = \frac{A}{H^2 * N} \quad (\text{Eq. S1.2})$$

992 Where *RS* is relative spacing, *A* is the modeled stand area, *H* is the mean tree height in the modeled
993 stand, and *N* is the number of trees in the modeled stand.

994

995 Underplanting occurs when the remaining stand's RS after harvesting is higher than the applied
996 underplanting threshold (i.e. stand density is lower). Otherwise, replanting is postponed and
997 reevaluated after the next thinning or harvesting intervention. Under continuous underplanting, the
998 number of stems replanted is determined by the stems necessary to re-establish the initial planting
999 density (in stems/ha).

1000 Finally, we regulated the maximum number of tree generations that were allowed to exist within a
1001 modeled stand simultaneously for each species. For even-aged managed stands (including stands
1002 managed under retention forestry practices) 1 generation was allowed, for stands managed under
1003 shelterwood cutting practices 2 generations were allowed (but replanting was only allowed after the
1004 shelterwood cutting took place), and for stands managed under selective harvesting practices 5
1005 generations were allowed.

1006

1007 II. Optimizing CTN management parameters

1008 In the management optimization we optimized the management parameters (i.e. thinning, harvesting,
1009 and replanting parameters) to maximize the stands' net present value (NPV) (Eq. S1.3).

$$1010 \quad \max\{NPV_{BA1, BA2, HP, RS}\} \quad (\text{Eq. S1.3})$$

1011 Where *NPV* is the NPV of the modeled stand, *BA1* is the applied upper basal area threshold to initiate
1012 thinning, *BA2* is the applied target basal area after thinning, *HP* are the applied harvesting parameters

1013 further specified for each CTN management practice in Supplementary, and *RS* is the applied relative
 1014 spacing threshold for underplanting.

1015
 1016 The different CTN management practices differed in the harvesting parameters that were included in
 1017 the optimization. The individual harvesting parameters for each management practice and the applied
 1018 parameter bounds can be found in Table S1.2.

1019 *Table S1.2 Harvesting parameters for each management practice and parameters bound applied in the optimization*

Management practice	Harvesting parameters		Included in optimization	Parameter bounds	
	Type	Description		Lower	Upper
Even-aged	Target mean dbh	Species-specific target mean dbh. When this mean dbh threshold is exceeded all trees of the respective species are harvested	Yes	10 cm	60 cm
Retention forestry	Target mean dbh	<i>See above</i>	Yes	10 cm	60 cm
	Area retained	Size area that remains unharvested. Preset to 10%.	No		
Shelterwood cutting	Target mean dbh	<i>See above</i> – when only one species remains in the stands the shelterwood cutting sequence is initiated	Yes	10 cm	60 cm
	Shelterwood BA	The remaining BA left as shelter during final harvesting	Yes	0 m ² /ha	40 m ² /ha
	Shelterwood time	Time shelter trees are left in the stand before also being harvested	Yes	1 year	15 years
Selective harvesting	Individual target dbh	Species-specific target dbh. Tree individuals with larger dbh are harvested during the harvest interventions	Yes	10 cm	60 cm
	Time of first harvesting	Preset to year 15	No		

Harvesting interval	The time between harvesting interventions	Yes	1 year	15 years
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1022 [Supplementary 2 – Optimized management parameters and supporting](#)
1023 [results](#)

1024 The following Supplementary present the management parameters for the CTN-managed stands and
1025 monocultures under optimized management, and additional results supporting the main text results
1026 and discussion.

1027

1028 [I. Optimized management parameters](#)

1029 Figure S2.1 Optimized management parameters for mixed-species stands under even-aged
1030 management-Figure S2.5 Optimized management parameters for monoculture stands under even-
1031 aged management show the optimized management parameters for CTN-managed stands established
1032 from bare land or by transforming mature monoculture stands. Figure 5 shows the optimized
1033 management parameters for Even-aged monocultures.

1034

1035 Even-aged management

1036

1037 *Figure S2.1 Optimized management parameters for mixed-species stands under even-aged management*

1038 Retention Forestry

1039

1040 *Figure S2.2 Optimized management parameters for mixed-species stands under retention forest management*

1042

1043 *Figure S2.3 Optimized management parameters for mixed-species stands under shelterwood cutting management*

1044 Selective harvesting

1045

1046 *Figure S2.4 Optimized management parameters for mixed-species stands under selective harvesting management*

1047

1048 Even-aged monocultures

1049

1050 *Figure S2.5 Optimized management parameters for monoculture stands under even-aged management*

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1052 II. Supporting results

1053

1054 Economic performance when monocultures do not receive carbon payments

1055

1056 *Figure S2.6 The economic potential of CTN-managed plantations evaluated based on two establishment scenarios: (A)*
 1057 *reforestation of bare land and (B) transformation of mature even-aged monoculture plantations. In the "Timber" valuation*
 1058 *scenario, only revenues from timber sales were considered. In the "pC10", "pC50", and "pC100" scenarios, payments for*
 1059 *carbon credits were also included in the valuation at prices of 10, 50, and 100 USD/tCO₂e, respectively. The horizontal lines*
 1060 *in the figure represent the economic potential of even-aged monoculture plantations managed solely for timber production.*

1061

1062 Figure S2.6 shows the comparison between the economic performance of CTN-managed mixed-
 1063 species stands and even-aged monocultures if monocultures also receive carbon payments. It can be
 1064 seen, that when monocultures do not receive carbon payments, the CTN-managed stands would then
 1065 consistently outperform monocultures at any carbon prices above 10 USD/tCO₂e.

1066

1067 Carbon storage when monocultures also received carbon payments

1068 Figure S2.7 shows the comparison between the carbon storage performance of CTN-managed mixed-
 1069 species stands and even-aged monocultures if monocultures also receive carbon payments. It can be

1070 seen, that when monocultures do not receive carbon payments, most CTN-managed stands able to
 1071 consistently outperform monocultures at carbon prices above 10 USD/tCO₂e.

1072
 1073 *Figure S2.7 Mid-term mean stand carbon stored in living trees by (A) reforesting bare land or (B) transforming mature even-*
 1074 *aged monoculture plantations. In the "Timber" valuation scenario, only revenues from timber sales were taken into account.*
 1075 *In the "pC10," "pC50," and "pC100" valuation scenarios, payments for carbon credits were also included at carbon prices of*
 1076 *10, 50, and 100 USD/tCO₂e, respectively. The horizontal lines in different colors show the carbon storage potential of even-*
 1077 *aged monoculture plantations managed solely for timber production.*

1078
 1079 Biodiversity indicators when monocultures also receive carbon payments (establishment from
 1080 bare land)

1081 Figure S2.8 shows the comparison between the biodiversity indicator values of CTN-managed mixed-
 1082 species stands established on bare land and even-aged monocultures if monocultures do not receive
 1083 carbon payments.

1084

1085 *Figure S2.8 Key biodiversity indicators of CTN-managed plantations established by reforesting bare land. In valuation*
 1086 *scenario "Timber" only revenues from timber sales were considered in the valuation. In the "Timber" valuation scenario, only*
 1087 *revenues from timber sales were taken into account. In the "pC10," "pC50," and "pC100" valuation scenarios, payments for*
 1088 *carbon credits were also included at carbon prices of 10, 50, and 100 USD/tCO₂e, respectively. The horizontal lines in*
 1089 *different colors show the biodiversity potential of even-aged monoculture plantations managed solely for timber production.*

1090

1091 **Planting cost reduction to break even**

1092 **Figure S2.9** Planting cost reduction to break even with the best-performing monocultures shows the
 1093 reduction in planting costs required for CTN-managed stands to break even with the best-performing
 1094 monocultures. Partly costs reductions above 100% would be required. Accordingly, reduced planting
 1095 costs, e.g. by using natural regeneration costs, are unlikely to be a significant driver of CTN
 1096 competitiveness.

1097

1098 *Figure S2.9 Planting cost reduction to break even with the best-performing monocultures*

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